
TEACHING PRACTICES OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN A PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN THE PHILIPPINES: IMPACT ON THE PROGRESS OF STUDENTS WITH LANGUAGE IMPAIRMENT

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ABSTRACT

ALOP, ANNALYN V., 2024. TEACHING PRACTICES OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN A PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN THE PHILIPPINES: IMPACT ON THE PROGRESS OF STUDENTS WITH LANGUAGE IMPAIRMENT. National University, Manila. 120 pp.

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Special education teachers frequently face students with varied degrees of verbal ability. Learners are nonverbal, making it difficult to measure their language abilities (Cablao, et.al, 2020). This study paper investigates the competency and pedagogical strategies used by special education teachers to cope with the barriers associated with language impairment, with a specific emphasis on presenting a tailored intervention plan meant to improve student progress. It covered four key questions: (1) teachers' competence in teaching students with language impairments, (2) the use of pedagogical strategies, (3) the impact of classroom practices on student progress, and (4) creating a teaching framework that can be used to facilitate teaching among students with language impairment. Special education teachers were the respondents from the selected schools that cater to special education centers, including Julian Felipe Elementary, Ladislao Diwa Elementary, and Manuel S. Rojas Elementary schools, emphasizing those with at least three years of experience.

The study highlights the importance of teacher competence, pedagogical strategies, and the impact on student's progress. Teachers with experience, specialized training, and certifications prove higher competence in addressing these students. An effective pedagogical strategy, including differentiated instruction, technology instruction, and individualized support is essential for creating inclusive and supportive classrooms. The impact of classroom practices with collaborative efforts from educators, families, and communities is essential for the student's progress. Effective teaching frameworks and continued professional development were needed to improve students' progress. This program, supported by the Zero Reject Policy and entrenched in the Malaysia Education Blueprint 2013–2025, aims to increase all students' competencies and foster acceptance of special needs students in mainstream classrooms through

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meaningful teaching and learning practices (Maarof et al.,2023). This study has limitations, including the number of respondents, self reported data, focus on teacher perspectives, cross-sectional, and the need for longitudinal studies. Future research should regularly examine and improve the strategies employed to keep them relevant and up to date. By acknowledging these limitations, future research can close these gaps and build on the results of the current study, contributing to the development of more comprehensive and trustworthy recommendations for the best ways to instruct language-impaired students.

Keywords: *Language impairment, Pedagogical Strategies, Teachers' Competence, Teaching framework, Students' Progress*

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